

Study of the Transient Voltage of the Silicon Solar Cell with Multi Vertical Junctions Connected in Parallel and Placed in Opened Circuit: Influence of Temperature and Magnetic Field on Transient Decay

Pape DIOP¹, Babou DIONE¹, Pape Touty TRAORE¹, Papa Monzon Alassane SAMAKE¹, Fatima BA¹ and Mamadou Lamine SAMB²

¹Laboratoire des Semi-conducteurs et d'Energie Solaire, Faculté des Sciences et Techniques, Université Cheikh Anta Diop, Dakar, Sénégal

²Iba DER THIAM University of Thiès, Sénégal
badione2016@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

This work consists in studying the transient voltage of a silicon solar cell with vertical junctions connected in parallel under polychromatic illumination and under the influence of temperature and magnetic field, in open circuit transient operation. The experimental device of the transient decay who occurs between two operating points in steady state is presented. The effect of the potential difference between two operating points on the voltage amplitude is also studied. Indeed, the influence of the optimum temperature on the transient decay and on the amplitude of the voltage is also studied. This optimum temperature is obtained by determining the optimum thickness from a given magnetic field.

Key words Silicon Solar Cell, Vertical Parallel Junction, Magnetic Field, Temperature, Time Constant, Base Thickness, Transient Voltage

1. INTRODUCTION

The silicon solar cells being under different technologies [1] have been the subject of several research works. They have undergone many changes in their structures.

The study models and the techniques used are essentially aimed at determining the phenomenological parameters [2, 3, 4], which influence the electrical parameters [5, 6, 7, 28], which are the series and shunt resistances, as well as than the capacity of the space charge area.

New architectures of solar cells have been produced, such as vertical junction solar cells (series or parallel) where the illumination is done parallel (or laterally) to the junction plane [8, 9], monofacial [10, 11] (front or rear face illumination), bifacial [12, 13] where illumination can be performed either from the front and the rear or simultaneously from both sides.

Vertical junction solar cells also called Vertical Multi Junctions (MJV) [14, 15, 16].

These structures are made from materials that are poor in electronic quality. The electronic quality is evaluated from phenomenological parameters [17, 18, 19, 20] which are the lifetime, the diffusion coefficient, the diffusion length and the mobility of the minority charge carriers, in the different regions of the solar cell, more particularly the base. By the surface which limit the various zones, the surface recombination speeds [21, 22, 23, 24, 25, 26] are also parameters which make it possible to evaluate the performance of the solar cell, which can be studied according to the models at one dimension [9, 27] or three dimensions [29,30] of space, under the conditions of operating regimes, which are: the static regime [31, 32], the transient dynamic regime [33, 34, 35, 36, 37] or frequency dynamics [38, 39, 40, 41].

Under these operating regimes, the solar cell may be subject to external conditions, which may be: temperature variations [42, 43], electromagnetic field variations [44, 45, 46, 47, 48], etc...

In regards to transient states, we can note, open circuit voltage decay (OCVD), the most popular technique, photocurrent decay (PCD) method [49], light-induced transient phase measurements photocurrent and voltage (SLIM-PCV), microwave photocurrent decay (MWPCD) [50].

In this work, we are interested in the study of a silicon solar cell (n/p) with vertical junctions connected in parallel, in transient state and placed under the double condition of temperature and magnetic field. This regime occurs between two stable states by operating points depending on two variable resistors. This technique makes it possible to obtain a transient decay at any operating point on the static I-V characteristic between two points close to the open circuit of the solar cell under illumination [51, 52]. We examine the effects of external conditions by variation of the temperature [53, 54], the magnetic field [55, 56] and the optimal thickness [57, 58] on the transient voltage and on the time (t_0) initiating their exponential decay [60], which delimits the conditions for experimental measurement of the time constant.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Experimental apparatus

Figure 1 presents the experimental device used to obtain the transient state by variations of the operating point of the solar cell [35, 36, 37].

Fig. 1 Experimental device for the characterization of the solar cell

This experimental device includes a BRI8500 square wave generator which drives an RFP50N06 type MOSFET transistor, two adjustable resistors R_1 and R_2 . The silicon solar cell placed under temperature and magnetic field, is subjected to constant multispectral lighting. A digital oscilloscope and a microcomputer are used for signal acquisition and processing. The transient decay occurs according to the following procedure, described below.

At time $t < 0$ (figure 1), the solar cell being under constant multi-spectral illumination, the MOSFET transistor is open and the solar cell is closed in series with the resistor R_2 alone: this corresponds to the operating point F_2 in steady state [51, 52] giving the potential V_2 . At $t = 0$ (figure 1), the closing of the MOSFET begins and after a very short time the MOSFET is completely closed, then the resistor R_1 is in parallel with R_2 this corresponds to the operating point F_1 , therefore the voltage V_2 goes to V_1 .

By varying R_1 and R_2 , the steady state operating points F_1 and F_2 move over the I-V characteristic (Figure 2), to produce a transient state.

Fig. 2 Illuminated I-V curve under constant magnetic field ($B3 < B2 < B1$) with two specific operating points

In figure 3, the structure of the (n/p) silicon solar cell with vertical junctions connected in parallel under magnetic field and temperature is presented.

Fig. 3 Structure of (n/p) solar cell with vertical junctions connected in parallel

Fig. 4 Structure of a vertical junction (n/p) solar cell

The rate of generation $G(z)$ of excess minority carriers which depends on the depth of absorption z of light in the base is given by the following relationship:

$$G(z) = \sum_{i=1}^3 a_i \exp(-b_i z) \tag{1}$$

The coefficients a_i and b_i are obtained through tabulated values of the radiation [64].

During the experiment, the level of illumination remains constant, which implies that the level of injection is not modified with respect to time. We obtain the magneto-transport equation [22, 46] in dynamic regime, relating to the excess of charge carriers $\delta(x, t)$ [27], in the base at the temperature (T) [42]:

$$D^* \cdot \frac{\partial^2 \delta(x, t)}{\partial x^2} - \frac{\delta(x, t)}{\tau} = \frac{\partial \delta(x, t)}{\partial t} \tag{2}$$

The diffusion coefficient D^* of the minority carriers in the base under the influence of the temperature T and the applied magnetic field B, is given by the relationship [46, 59]:

$$D^* = D^*(B, T) = \frac{D(T)}{1 + [\mu(T) \times B]^2} \tag{3}$$

τ is the average lifetime of minority carriers in the base.

$$\mu(T) = 1,43 \cdot 10^9 T^{2,42} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ V}^{-1} \text{ S}^{-1} \tag{4}$$

$\mu(T)$ is the mobility of minority carriers in the base [62]

B is the magnetic field in the base.

The diffusion coefficient of the minority carriers of charge in the base, dependent on the temperature D(T) without magnetic field is given by the relation of Einstein-Smoluchowski:

$$D(T) = \mu(T) \cdot \frac{K_B \cdot T}{q} \tag{5}$$

Where K_b is the Boltzmann constant $K_b = 1,38 \cdot 10^{-23} \text{ m}^2 \text{ kg s}^{-2} \text{ K}^{-1}$ and q the elementary charge of the electron.

The equation is solved using the following boundary conditions:

- at the junction $x=0$:

$$D^* \cdot \frac{\partial \delta(x, t)}{\partial x} \Big|_{x=0} = S_f \cdot \delta(0, t) \tag{6}$$

- In the middle of the base:

$$D^* \cdot \frac{\partial \delta(x, t)}{\partial x} \Big|_{x=\frac{H}{2}} = 0 \tag{7}$$

S_f is the recombination velocity of the minority charge carriers at the junction [23, 25, 37] and defines the operating point of the solar cell [15, 51, 52] on its I-V characteristic.

The system of equations (2), (6) and (7) constitutes a problem of Sturm Liouville [63] whose solutions are with separable variables of the type:

$$\delta(x, t) = X(x) \cdot T(t) \tag{8}$$

$X(x)$ represents the spatial part of the minority carrier density and $T(t)$ the temporal part.

$X(x)$ and $T(t)$ take the following forms respectively:

$$X(x) = A_1 \cos\left(\frac{\omega x}{\sqrt{D^*}}\right) + A_2 \sin\left(\frac{\omega x}{\sqrt{D^*}}\right) \tag{9}$$

$$T(t) = T(0) \cdot \exp\left(-\left(\omega^2 + \frac{1}{\tau}\right)t\right) \tag{10}$$

$$\text{With } \frac{1}{\tau_c} = \frac{1}{\tau} + \omega^2 \quad (11)$$

The application of the boundary conditions (6) and (7) give respectively the relations (12) and (13):

$$\frac{\omega\sqrt{D^*}}{S_f} = \frac{A_1}{A_2} = \gamma \quad (12)$$

$$\tan\left(\frac{\omega.H}{2\sqrt{D^*}}\right) = \frac{S_f}{\omega\sqrt{D^*}} \quad (13)$$

Equation (13) is a transcendental equation whose solutions are determined graphically.

$$\text{With : } \frac{\omega.H}{2\sqrt{D^*}} \in \left[0, \frac{\pi}{2}\right] \cup \left[\left(n - \frac{1}{2}\right)\pi; \left(n + \frac{1}{2}\right)\pi\right] \quad (14)$$

The first interval $\left[0, \frac{\pi}{2}\right]$ suit for $n=0$ and the second for $n > 0$.

When $n=0$, we have the first term $\delta_0(x, t)$ that corresponds to the fundamental state with the eigenvalue. And for $n > 0$, we have the different $\delta_n(x, t)$ harmonics of order n of eigenvalues .

A_1 and A_2 are calculated using the normalization conditions and the Fourier transformation.

The expression of $T_n(0)$ is calculated using the density of minority carriers in the static regime.

The expression of $\delta(x, t)$ is therefore written:

$$\delta(x, z, t, T, B) = \sum \delta_n(x, z, t, T, B) = \sum X_n(x) \cdot T_n(z, T, B, 0) \cdot \exp\left(-\frac{1}{\tau_{c,n}} t\right) \quad (15)$$

The density of excess charge minority carriers in the base is given by relation (16).

$$\delta(x, z, t, T, B) = \sum_n \delta_n(x, z, t, T, B) \quad (16)$$

$\tau_{c,n}$ is called decay time constant, its inverse can be written:

$$\frac{1}{\tau_{c,n}} = \frac{1}{\tau_0} + \omega_n^2 \quad (17)$$

The expression of the voltage collected at the terminals of the solar cell when it submitted to polychromatic illumination is obtained from the Boltzmann relationship; it is expresses in the form:

$$V(t) = q_0 \cdot Fc(\omega_0) \cdot \exp\left(-\frac{t}{\tau_{c,0}}\right) \quad (18)$$

$$\text{With } Fc(\omega_0) = \frac{A_0 \cdot T_0(0)}{\delta(0,0)}$$

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Transient Voltage

The solutions of the transcendental equation as well as the expression for the minority carrier density $\delta(x, t)$ allowed us to plot the profiles of the transient voltage in the base using the results of the optimum base thickness (Hopt) [55, 56] for different magnetic fields (B) and values of the optimum temperature, border between normal phenomena and the Umklapp process [59].

The following figures represent the evolution of the transient voltage as a function of (Hopt), of the magnetic field (B) and of (Topt).

Fig. 5 Transient photo voltage decay versus the time $t(s)$ for different values of ΔV $S_f=10\text{cm/s}$;
 $T_{op}=254.7\text{K}$ $B=0.0003\text{T}$; $H_{opt}=0.0161\text{cm}$; $z=0.017\text{cm}$; $\tau=10^5\text{s}$

Fig. 6 Transient photo voltage decay versus the time $t(s)$ for different values of ΔV $S_f=10\text{cm/s}$;
 $T_{op}=286.6\text{K}$; $B=0.0004\text{T}$; $H_{opt}=0.0156\text{cm}$; $z=0.017\text{cm}$; $\tau=10^5\text{s}$

Fig. 7 Transient photovoltage decay versus the time $t(s)$ for different values of ΔV $S_f=10\text{cm/s}$;
 $T_{op}=336.5\text{K}$; $B=0.0005\text{T}$; $H_{opt}=0.0153\text{cm}$; $z=0.017\text{cm}$; $\tau=10^5\text{s}$

Fig. 8 Transient photovoltage decay versus the time $t(s)$ for different values of ΔV Sf=10cm/s; Top=336.5K; B=0.0006T; Hopt =0.0149cm; z=0.017cm; $\tau=10^5$ s

Fig. 9 Transient photovoltage decay versus the time $t(s)$ for different values of ΔV Sf=10cm/s; Top=361.4K; B=0.0007T; Hopt =0.0147cm; z=0.017cm; $\tau=10^5$ s

Fig. 10 Transient photo voltage decay versus the time $t(s)$ for different values of ΔV Sf=10cm/s; Top=381.9K; B=0.0008T; Hopt =0.0146cm; z=0.017cm; $\tau=10^5$ s

Fig. 11 Transient photo voltage decay versus the time $t(s)$ for different values of ΔV $S_f=10\text{cm/s}$;
 $T_{op}=410\text{K}$; $B=0.0009\text{T}$; $H_{opt}=0.01445\text{cm}$; $z=0.017\text{cm}$; $\tau=10^{-5}\text{s}$

Fig. 12 Transient photo voltage decay versus the time $t(s)$ for different values of ΔV $S_f=10\text{cm/s}$;
 $T_{op}=418.8\text{K}$; $B=0.001\text{T}$; $H_{opt}=0.0143\text{cm}$; $z=0.017\text{cm}$; $\tau=10^{-5}\text{s}$

We observe in figures 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11 and 12 a slow decay of the transient photovoltage as the temperature increases. Indeed, when the temperature constantly increases, there will be thermal agitation. As a result, the carriers will take longer to arrive at the final steady state, hence a slow decay with increasing temperature. We also observe a decrease in the amplitude of the transient photovoltage with increasing temperature and magnetic field. In addition, the thermal agitation leads to the increase of the intrinsic density of carriers at the level of the junction, therefore the reduction of the photovoltage and the increase of the transient decay with the increase of the optimal temperature. Almost all of the carriers stored at the junction will not cross there when S_f tends to zero. We must therefore expect an open circuit voltage greater than that of the short circuit voltage.

4. CONCLUSION

This work allowed us to see the effect of temperature and magnetic field on the transient photovoltage of a parallel vertical junction silicon solar cell. It also allowed us to see the effect of the potential difference on the photovoltage amplitude. After the graphical resolution of the transcendental equation, we could observe that the eigenvalues and the decay time constants obtained are dependent on the optimal temperature. Increasing the thickness of the base results in an acceleration of the decay time.

An increase of the magnetic field leads an increase of the temperature (Umklapp), therefore the same effect of increasing the decay time and a decrease of the amplitude of the photovoltage corresponding to a reduction in the optimum thickness is obtained from the base.

REFERENCES

- [1]. M. A. Green, (March 1995). Silicon Solar cells advanced principles & practice Printed by Bridge printer Pty. Ltd. 29-35 Dunning Avenue, Roseberry, Center for photovoltaic Devices and systems; pp.29-35.
- [2]. Gaubas, E. and Vanhellemont, J. (1996). A Simple Technique for the Separation of Bulk and Surface Recombination Parameters in Silicon. *Journal of Applied Physics*, 80, 6293-6297. <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.363705>.
- [3]. Gupta, S., Ahmed, P. and Garg, S. (1988). A Method for the Determination of the Material parameters τ , D, L, S and τ from Measured Short-Circuit Photocurrent. *Solar Cells*, 25, 61-72. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0379-6787\(88\)90058-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/0379-6787(88)90058-0).
- [4]. J.H. Scofiels (1995). Effects of series resistance and inductance on solar cell admittance measurements. *Solar energy materials and solar cells*, 37(2), 217-233.
- [5]. M Chegaar, Z Ouennoughi, A Hoffmann (2001). A new method for evaluating illuminated solar cell parameters. *Solid-State Electronics* Vol. 45, issue 2, Pp. 293-296. [http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/s0038-1101\(00\)00277-x](http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/s0038-1101(00)00277-x)
- [6]. Nobuyuki Andoh, Kenichi Hayashi, Takatoshi Shirasawa, Toshiyuki Sameshima, Koichi Kamisako (2001). Effect of film thickness on electrical property of microcrystalline silicon *Solar Energy Materials and Solar Cells*, Vol. 66 issue 1-4 Pp. 437-441 [http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/s0927-0248\(00\)00205-1](http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/s0927-0248(00)00205-1)
- [7]. M. Bashahu and A. Habyarimana (1995). Review and test of methods for determination of the solar cell series resistance. *Renewable Energy*, 6, 2, pp. 127-138, [https://doi.org/10.1016/0960-1481\(94\)E0021-V](https://doi.org/10.1016/0960-1481(94)E0021-V)
- [8]. Wise, J.F. (1970). Vertical Junction Hardened Solar Cell. US Patent 3, 690-953.
- [9]. Gover, A. and Stella, P. (1974). Vertical Multijunction Solar-Cell One-Dimensional Analysis. *IEEE Transactions on Electron Devices*, ED-21, 351-356. <https://doi.org/10.1109/T-ED.1974.17927>.
- [10]. G. Sahin, M. Dieng, M. A. O. El Moujtaba, M. I. Ngom, A. Thiam, G. Sissoko. (2015). Capacitance of Vertical Parallel Junction Silicon Solar Cell Under Monochromatic Modulated Illumination. *Journal of Applied Mathematics and Physics*, 3, 1536-1543.
- [11]. Fossum, J.G. and Burgess, E.L. (1978) High Efficiency p+-n-n+ Back-Surface-Field Solar Cells. *Applied Physics Letters*, 33, 238-240. <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.90311>
- [12]. Meier, D.L., Hwang, J.-M. and Campbell, R.B. (1988) The Effect of Doping Density and Injection Level on Minority Carrier Lifetime as Applied to Bifacial Dendritic Web Silicon Solar Cells. *IEEE Transactions on Electron Devices*, 35, 70-79. <https://doi.org/10.1109/16.2417>
- [13]. Luque, A., Ruiz, J.M., Cuevas, A., Eguren, J. and Agost, M.G. (1997). Double Side Solar Cells to Improve Static Concentrator. *Photovoltaic Solar Energy Conference*, Luxembourg, 269-277. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-94-009-9840-7_25
- [14]. M. Meusel, W. Benssch, T. Berdunde, R. Kern, V. Khorenko, W. Kostler, G. Laroche, T. Torunski, W. Zimmermann, G. Strobl, W. Guter, M Hermlle, R. Hoheisel, G Siefer, E Welsler,

- F. Dimroth, A. W. Bett, W. Geens, C. Baur, S. Taylor, G. Hey. (2007). Development and production of European III-V multijunction Solar cells. Proceeding of the 22nd European photovoltaic Solar Energy Conference. Pp. 16 – 51.
- [15]. Diallo, H.L., Dieng, B., Ly, I., Dione, M.M., Ndiaye, M., Lemrabott, O.H., Bako, Z.N., Wereme, A. and Sissoko, G. (2012). Determination of the Recombination and Electrical Parameters of a Vertical Multijunction Silicon Solar Cell. *Research Journal of Applied Sciences, Engineering and Technology*, 4, 2626-2631.
- [16]. Ayvazian, G.E., Kirakosyan, G.H. and Minasyan, G.A. (2004). Characteristics of Solar Cells with Vertical p-n Junction. Proceedings of 19th European Photovoltaic Solar Energy Conference, Paris, 7-11 June 2004, 117-119.
- [17]. K. Taretto, U. Rau, Thomas A. Wagner, Jens Werner (2003). A Simple Method to Extract the Diffusion Length from the Output Parameters of Solar Cells - Application to Polycrystalline Silicon. *Solid State Phenomena* Vol. 93, Pp 399-404 <http://dx.doi.org/10.4028/www.scientific.net/ssp.93.399>
- [18]. R. R. Vardanyan, U. Kerst, P. Wawer, H. Wagemann, (1998). Method for measurement of all recombination parameters in the base region of solar cells. 2nd World conference and exhibition on photovoltaic solar energy conversion 6-10 july, Vol I; pp, 191-193
- [19]. K. Misiakos, C. H. Wang, A. Neugroschel and F. A. Lindholm (1990). Simultaneous extraction of minoritycarrier parameters in crystalline semiconductors by lateral photocurrent. *J.Appl. Phys.* 67(1): 321-333.
- [20]. Jurg Waldmeyer (1988). A contactless method for determination of carrier lifetime, surface recombination velocity, and diffusion constant in semiconductors; *J. Appl. Phys.* 63(6), 15, pp. 1977-1983.
- [21]. Wang, C.H. and Neugroschel, A. (1987). Minority-Carrier Lifetime and Surface Recombination Velocity Measurement by Frequency-Domain Photoluminescence. *IEEE Transaction on Electron Devices*, 38, 2169-2180. <https://doi.org/10.1109/16.83745>
- [22]. Th. Flohr and R. Helbig (1989). Determination of minority-carrier lifetime and Surface recombination velocity by optical beam induced current measurements at different light wavelengths. *J. Appl. Phys.*, 66(7), 3060-3065.
- [23]. Bocande, Y.L., Correa, A., Gaye, I., Sow, M.L. and Sissoko, G. (1994) Bulk and Surfaces Parameters Determination in High Efficiency Si Solar Cells. Proceedings of the World Renewable Energy Congress, Pergamon, Part III, Vol. 3, 1698-1700
- [24]. Jung, T.W., Lindholm, F.A. and Neugroschel, A (1984). Unifying View of Transient Responses for Determining Lifetime and Surface Recombination Velocity in Silicon Diodes and Back-Surface-Field Solar Cells, with Application to Experimental Short-Circuit-Current Decay. *IEEE Transactions on Electron Devices*, 31, 588-595. <https://doi.org/10.1109/T-ED.1984.21573>
- [25]. G. Sissoko, C. Museruka, A. Corréa, I. Gaye and A. L. Ndiaye (1996). Light spectral effect on recombination parameters of silicon solar cell. *Renewable Energy*, Vol 3, pp.1487-1490. Pergamon, 0960-1481
- [26]. O. Diasse, A. Diao, M. Wade, M. S. Diouf, I. Diatta, R. Mane, Y. Traore and G. Sissoko (2018). Back surface recombination velocity modeling in white bias silicon solar cell under steady state. *World Journal of Condensed Matter Physics*, 9, (1), pp. 189-201.

- [27]. Wafaa Abd El-Basit, Ashraf Mosleh Abd El-Maksood and Fouad Abd El-Moniem Saad Soliman (2013). Mathematical Model for Photovoltaic Cells. Leonardo Journal of Sciences, Issue 23, pp.13-28. <http://ljs.academicdirect.org/>
- [28]. M.M. Dione, H. Ly Diallo, M. Wade, I. Ly, M. Thiame, F. Toure, A. Gueye Camara, N. Dieme, Z. Nouhou Bako, S. Mbodji, F. I. Barro, G. Sissoko. Determination of the shunt and series resistances of a vertical multijunction solar cell under constant multispectral light. 26th European Photovoltaic Solar Energy Conference and Exhibition (2010), pp. 250-254.
- [29]. Diallo, H.L., Maiga, A.S., Wereme, A. and Sissoko, G. (2008) New Approach of both Junction and Back Surface Recombination Velocities in a 3D Modelling Study of a Polycrystalline Silicon Solar Cell. The European Physical Journal Applied Physics, 42, 193-211. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1051/epjap:2008085>
- [30]. A. M. M. Kosso, M. Thiame, Y. Traore, I. Diatta, M. Ndiaye, L. Habiboullah, I. Ly, G. Sissoko, (2018). 3D Study of a Silicon Solar Cell under Constant Monochromatic Illumination: Influence of Both, Temperature and Magnetic Field. Journal of Scientific and Engineering Research, 5(7):259-269.
- [31]. Sissoko, G., Nanema, E., Correa, A., Biteye, P.M., Adj, M. and Ndiaye, A. L (1998). Silicon Solar cell recombination parameters determination using the illuminated I-V characteristic. Renewable Energy, Elsevier Science Ltd, 0960-1481/#. Vol-3, pp.1848–1851.
- [32]. Dieye. M, Mbodji. S, Zoungrana. M, Zerbo. I, Dieng. B and Sissoko. G. (2015) A 3D Modelling of Solar Cell's Electric Power under Real Operating Point. World Journal of Condensed Matter Physics, 5, 275-283. doi: 10.4236/wjcmp.2015.54028
- [33]. B. Ba, M. Kane, A. Fickou, G. Sissoko (1993). Excess minority carrier densities and transient short circuit currents in polycrystalline silicon solar cells. Solar Energy Materials and Solar cells 31 pp. 33-49 0927-0248 /93/\$ 06.00 © 1993 Elsevier Science Publishers B. V.
- [34]. Joardar. K., Dondero. R.C. and Schroda. D.K (1989). Critical Analysis of the Small-Signal Voltage-Decay Technique for Minority-Carrier Lifetime Measurement in Solar Cells. Solid State Electronics, 32, pp.479-483. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0038-1101\(89\)90030-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/0038-1101(89)90030-0)
- [35]. P. Mialhe, G. Sissoko, F. Pelanchon, and J. M. Salagnon (1992). Régimes transitoires des photopiles: durée de vie des porteurs et vitesse de recombinaison. J. Phys. III, France 2 pp. 2317-2331.
- [36]. K.M. Sy, A. Diene, S. Tamba, M. S. Diouf, I. Diatta, M. Dieye, Y. Traore, G. Sissoko (2016). Effect of temperature on transient decay induced by charge removal of a silicon solar cell under constant illumination. Journal of Scientific and Engineering Research, 3(6): 433-445.
- [37]. G. Sissoko, S. Sivoththanam, M. Rodot, P. Mialhe, (1992). Constant illumination-induced open circuit voltage decay (CIOVD) method, as applied to high efficiency Si Solar cells for bulk and back surface characterization. 11th European Photovoltaic Solar Energy Conference and Exhibition (Montreux, Switzerland). Pp. 352-54.
- [38]. Mandelis, A. (1989) Coupled Ac Photocurrent and Photothermal Reflectance Response Theory of Semiconducting p-n Junctions. I. Journal of Applied Physics, 66, 5572-5583. <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.343662>
- [39]. Ly, I., Zerbo, I., Wade, M., Ndiaye, M., Dieng, A., Diao, A., Thiam, N., Thiam, A., Dione, M.M., Barro, F.I., Maiga, A.S. and Sissoko, G. (2011). Bifacial Silicon Solar Cell under Frequency Modulation and Monochromatic Illumination: Recombination Velocities and

- Associated Equivalent Electrical Circuits. Proceedings of 26th European Photovoltaic Solar Energy Conference and Exhibition, Hamburg, 5-9 September 2011, 298-301.
- [40]. Luc, B., Shahriar, M., Dean, H., Marco, S., Manuela, A. and Claudio, N. (1994). Investigation of Carrier Transport through Silicon Wafers by Photocurrent Measurement. *Journal of Applied Physics*, 75, 4000-4008. <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.356022>
- [41]. Honma, N., Munakata, C. and Shimizu, H. (1988). Calibration of Minority Carrier Lifetimes Measured with an Ac Photovoltaic Method. *Japanese Journal of Applied Physics*, 27, 1322-1326. <https://doi.org/10.1143/JJAP.27.1322>
- [42]. Fall, M., Gaye, I., Diarisso, D., Diop, G., Loum, K., Diop, N., Sy, K., Ndiaye, M. and Sissoko, G. (2021). AC Back Surface Recombination Velocity in n⁺-p-p⁺ Silicon Solar Cell under Monochromatic Light and Temperature. *Journal of Electromagnetic Analysis and Applications*, 13, 67-81. doi: 10.4236/jemaa.2021.135005.
- [43]. B.D.D. Sylla, I. Ly, O. Sow, B. Dione, Y. Traore, G. Sissoko, (2018). Junction Surface Recombination Concept as Applied to Silicon Solar Cell Maximum Power Point Determination Using Matlab/Simulink: Effect of Temperature. *Journal of Modern Physics*, 9, 172-188. <http://www.scirp.org/journal/jmp>
- [44]. Mbodji, S., Zoungrana, M., Zerbo, I., Dieng, B. and Sissoko, G. (2015) Modelling Study of Magnetic Field's Effects on Solar Cell's Transient Decay. *World Journal of Condensed Matter Physics*, 5, 284-293. doi: 10.4236/wjcmp.2015.54029.
- [45]. S. Mbodji, I. Ly, A. Dioum, H. Ly Diallo, I.F. Barro, G. Sissoko (2006). Equivalent electric circuit of a bifacial solar cell in transient state under magnetic field. Proceedings of the 21st European Photovoltaic Solar Energy Conference and Exhibition -Dresden, Germany, pp.447-450.
- [46]. Y. Betser, D. Ritter, G. Bahir, S. Cohen, and J. Sperling, "Measurement of the minority carrier mobility in the base of heterojunction bipolar transistors using a magnetotransport method", *Appl. Phys. Lett.*, Vol. 67, No. 13, (1995) p 1883-1884.
- [47]. S. Mbodji, A. S. Maiga, M. Dieng, A. Wereme, G. Sissoko (2009). Removal charge technique applied to a bifacial solar cell under a constant magnetic field *Global Journal of Pure and Applied Sciences*, Vol.15, N°1, pp.125-132.
- [48]. Madougou, S., Made, F., Boukary, M.S. and Sissoko, G. (2007) I-V Characteristics for Bifacial Silicon Solar Cell Studied under a Magnetic Field. *Advanced Materials Research*, 18-19, 303-312. <http://dx.doi.org/10.4028/www.scientific.net/AMR.18-19.303>
- [49]. Pisarkiewicz, T. (2004) Photodecay Method in Investigation of Materials and Photovoltaic Structures. *Opto-Electronics Review*, 12, 33-40.
- [50]. Schmidt, J. and Aberle, A.G. (1997) Accurate Method for the Determination of Bulk Minority-Carrier Lifetimes of Mono- and Multicrystalline Silicon Wafers. *Journal of Applied Physics*, 81, 6186-6199. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1063/1.364403>
- [51]. B. Dione, O. Sow, M. Wade, I. LY, S. Mbodji, G. Sissoko (2016). Experimental Processus for Acquisition Automatic Features of I-V Properties and Temperature of the Solar Panel by Changing the Operating Point. *Circuits and Systems*, 7, 3984-4000 <http://www.scirp.org/journal/cs> ISSN Online: 2153-1293 ISSN Print: 2153-1285.
- [52]. G. Sissoko and S. Mbodji (2011). A Method to Determine the Solar Cell Resistances from Single I-V Characteristic Curve Considering the Junction Recombination Velocity (Sf). *Int. J.*

- Pure Appl. Sci. Technol., 6(2), pp.103-114. ISSN 2229 – 6107 Available online at www.ijopaasat.in
- [53]. Ndiaye, F.M., Ba, M.L., Ba, M.A., Diop, G., Diatta, I., Sow, E.H., Mballo, O. and Sissoko, G. (2020) Lamella Silicon Optimum Width Determination under Temperature. *International Journal of Advanced Research*, 8, 1409-1419. <https://doi.org/10.21474/IJAR01/11228>
- [54]. M. N, Sow. O, Gueye. S, Traore. Y, Diatta. I, Thiam. A, Ba. M, Mane. R, Ly. I and Sissoko. G. (2019). Influence of Both Magnetic Field and Temperature on Silicon Solar Cell Base Optimum Thickness Determination. *Journal of Modern Physics*, 10, 1596-1605. doi: 10.4236/jmp.2019.1013105.
- [55]. C. Thiaw, M.L. Ba, M.A. Ba, G. Diop, I. Diatta, M. Ndiaye, G. Sissoko (2020). n⁺-p-p⁺ Silicon Solar Cell Base Optimum Thickness Determination under Magnetic Field. *Journal of Electromagnetic Analysis and Applications*, 12, pp. 103-113, ISSN Online: 1942-0749 ISSN Print: 1942-0730: <https://www.scirp.org/journal/paperabs.aspx?paperid=101717>
- [56]. Diop, G., Ba, H.Y., Thiam, N., Traore, Y., Dione, B., Ba, M.A., Diop, P., Diop, M.S., Mballo, O. and Sissoko, G (2019). Base Thickness Optimization of a Vertical Series Junction Silicon Solar Cell under Magnetic Field by the Concept of Back Surface Recombination Velocity of Minority Carrier. *ARNP Journal of Engineering and Applied Sciences*, 14, 4078-4085.
- [57]. [S. Dede, M., L. Ba, A. Ba, M. Ndiaye, M. Gueye, S. , Sow, E. , Diatta, I. , Diop, M. Wade, M. and Sissoko, G. (2020). Back Surface Recombination Velocity Dependent of Absorption Coefficient as Applied to Determine Base Optimum Thickness of an n⁺/p/p⁺ Silicon Solar Cell. *Energy and Power Engineering*, 12, 445-458. doi: 10.4236/epe.2020.127027.
- [58]. M.S. Diop, H.Y. Ba, N. Thiam, I. Diatta, Y. Traore, M.L. Ba, El H. Sow, O. Mballo, G. Sissoko (2019). Surface Recombination Concept as Applied to Determinate Silicon Solar Cell Base Optimum Thickness with Doping Level Effect. *World Journal of Condensed Matter Physics*, 9, 102-111. <https://doi.org/10.4236/wjcmp.2019.94008>
- [59]. Richard, M., Ibrahima, L., Mamadou, W., Ibrahima, D., Marcel, S.D., Youssou, T., Mor, N., Seni, T. and Grégoire, S. (2017). Minority Carrier Diffusion Coefficient D*(B, T): Study in Temperature on a Silicon Solar Cell under Magnetic Field. *Energy and Power Engineering*, 9, 1-10. <http://www.scirp.org/journal/epe>. <https://doi.org/10.4236/epe.2017.91001>
- [60]. P. Diop, S. Gueye, G. Diop, D. Faye, I. Diatta, O.K. Dieng, O. Sow, M. Thiame, M. Wade and G. Sissoko (2022). Influence de la température et du champ magnétique sur la décroissance transitoire de la densité des porteurs de charge dans une photopile au silicium a multi jonctions verticales connectées en parallèle et placée en circuit ouvert. *International journal of advanced research* doi: <http://dx.doi.org/10.21474/IJAR01/15150>
- [61]. Furlan, J. and Amon, S. (1985) Approximation of the Carrier Generation Rate in Illuminated Silicon. *Solid-State Electronics*, 28, 1241-1243. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0038-1101\(85\)90048-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/0038-1101(85)90048-6)
- [62]. Kunst, M., Muller, G., Schmidt, R. and Wetzal, H. (1988). Surface and Volume Decay Processes in Semiconductors Studied by Contactless Transient Photoconductivity Measurements. *Applied Physics*, 46, 77-85. <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF00615912>
- [63]. H. Reinhard (1987). *Equation aux dérivées partielles*. Dunod Université, Paris.

- [64]. Furlan, J. and Amon, S. (1985) Approximation of the Carrier Generation Rate in Illuminated Silicon. *Solid-State Electronics*, 28, 1241-1243. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0038-1101\(85\)90048-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/0038-1101(85)90048-6)